

INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON UNDERGRADUATES LOW PATRONAGE TO UNIVERSITY LIBRARY SERVICES IN SOKOTO STATE UNIVERSITY, SOKOTO

¹Jamilu Isah, ²Sadiq Aisha Yelwa and ³Bala Dan Amo

^{1,2,3}InuwaAbdulkadir Library, Sokoto State University
e-mail: jamiluisaharkilla@gmail.com

Abstract

The aim of the study was to determine the Influence of social media on Undergraduates' low patronage to university library services in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Three research questions were formulated to guide the study. The researcher used descriptive survey research design for the study. The population of the study comprises two thousand two hundred (2,200) Undergraduate students of the university, three hundred and twenty-one (321) were sampled using proportionate sampling technique. The questionnaire was titled Influence of Social Media on Undergraduate's Patronage Questionnaire (ISMUPQ). The instrument was face validated by three experts one from Measurement and Evaluation unit and two experts from Department of Library and Information Science, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Data collected was analyzed using frequency and percentage score. The major finding of the study revealed the extent of using social media such as: Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Badoo, Instagram, Messenger, YouTube by the Undergraduates which may eventually prevent them to patronize University library services. The findings showed that social media do not allow undergraduates to patronize library services, it affects students spelling and addiction to social media also affect students' academic life. It also revealed adoption of social media sites to disseminate information resources, maximum time should not be given to social media, organizes group discussion are the strategies to minimize the effect of social media and increase the level of patronage to university library services. In-conclusion some recommendations were made which includes: Libraries can also curtail the effect of social media by adopting social media sites to disseminate information resources, promote reading habit among undergraduates by organizing literacy activities such as book discussion, library orientation, library seminar and friendly demeanor of librarians, will go a long way.

Keywords: Social Media, Undergraduates, Library Patronage and Library services

Introduction

Undergraduate students who have access to computers and internet facilities prefer to browse, chat, send email, SMS, Facebook, yahoo messenger, play computer games. According to Encyclopedia of computer science (2012) Social networking sites are any website designed to allow multiple users to publish content of them. The information may be on any subject and may be for consumption by friends, mates, employers, employees just to mention a few.

Social media refers to the means of interactions among people in which they create, share, and exchange information and ideas in virtual communities and networks. Boyd and Ellison (2007) define social networking sites as Web-based services that allow individuals to construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, expressive a list of other

users with whom they share connections, view and negotiate their list of connections and those made by others within the system.

The advancement in technologies such as television, computer, social media and internet are expected to be agent of deteriorating reading habit among undergraduates which is a means of entertainment and getting information and enables us to create online presence very easily, but part of the side effect is that social media is reducing reading habit and decreasing the level of library patronage by the Undergraduate student. The main focus here is on social network not google or internet where electronic databases are found and readable (Barsky and Purdon, 2006). Despite the importance of technology, there is no substitute for books when it comes to encouraging reading and expanding imagination. Therefore, Undergraduates need to adequately patronize university library services (Humphrey, 2008). According to Reitz (2004), University Library is a library that is an integral part of a college, university or other institutions of postsecondary education, administered to meet the information and research needs of its students, faculty and staff. University library, therefore, is a type of library found in institutions of higher learning universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education that provide services to clientele in various format.

The library services are part of the library operations which involved the planned activities that are performed for the provision of the needed services to patrons. The patrons constitute the various categories of users of such services. The library operations are essentially administrative and technical process (Akintunde, 2006). The technical processes refer to the house-keeping functions, which Oni (2004) classified in to four sub-systems of acquisition, cataloguing, circulation and serial control. These sub-systems are the backbone of the services that can interface between the library and its users. The basic services that university libraries commonly offered have been enumerated as traditional and ICT based are what undergraduate ought to patronized effectively.

Library patronage is regarded to be a physical and remote access to and consultation or use of libraries' collections by undergraduate students and or any clientele in the university. Schoenberger (2018) stated that patronage of the library by intended users is a vital measure of output services provided by libraries. One of the fundamental laws of library is that the information resources such as books and non-book materials must be well consulted by the intended users. Library users are very significant in the practice of librarianship. This is because library practice revolves around the users.

Statement of the problem

The university library engages in provision of various services to its users which ranges from technical services to reader services (conventional and electronic services) .Social media has become a great concern to undergraduates whereby they become reluctant readers and addicted to social media, because they no longer see reading and writing as a pleasure, they prefer to watch events on the screen rather than read about them on the pages of paper. This problem seems to be as a result of the embracement of social media and interaction with new information technologies that Undergraduates may find it difficult to patronize the library

services available for their consumption. This study aim to investigate the Effect of social media on undergraduates patronage to University library services in Sokoto state, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the Influence of social media on Undergraduates low patronage to University library services in Sokoto state, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Determine the extent to which use social media is used by Undergraduates.
- ii. Ascertain the influence of social media to undergraduates low patronage to library services.
- iii. Find out the strategies to minimize influence of social media to undergraduate low patronage to library services.

Research Questions

The following are research questions formulated to guide the study:

What are the extents use of social media by Undergraduate?

What are the influence of social media to undergraduates low patronage to library services?

What are the strategies to minimize influence of social media to undergraduate low patronage to library services?

Literature Review

Concept of Social media

Social media could be seen as a process of communicating, interacting, marketing through Information Communication Technology and internet connectivity. Social media is a 21st century term used to broadly define a variety of networking tools or technologies that emphasized the social aspect of the internet as channel for communication, collaboration and creative expression (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). The examples of social media sites include: Facebook, twitter, WhatsApp, Instagram, Myspace, YouTube, LinkedIn, Wikipedia to mention but a few. Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) defined social media as “Internet based applications that allow the creation and exchange of content which is user generated”.

Influence of Social media on Undergraduates Low Patronage to University Library Services
Technologies are gashing our young people away from the good habit of reading. Technologies such as television; computer, social media and internet are gradually replacing reading as an accepted form of entertainment and getting information (Sudha and Kavitha, 2016). The emergence of social media simplified the process, because they do not call for advanced internet knowledge or experience and are made up of a wide array of different formats and topics. This means that anyone can connect through social media (Sudha & Kavitha, 2016). Preliminary investigations revealed that, nowadays undergraduates spend

more than two-hour chatting with friends, sending pictures, short clips, text and music that are contrary to their intellectual benefit, thus fail to achieve academic success.

Besides that, academic achievement is the ability of student to study, remember facts and being able to communicate their knowledge orally or in written form in an examination condition (Kpolovie, Joe & Okoto, 2014). Furthermore, Jha, Jaipuria, Jha, and Sinha (2016) asserted that students are more probably affected by social media to some extent, it absolutely affects the lives of undergraduate university student's academic performance. Kpolovie *et al* added that social media is attractive as it gives university students another world to make friends, also provides a good way to release pressure upon all this it takes students time, which may deny them to patronize and make judicious use of the abundance resources in the library.

Strategies to Minimize the Influence of Social Media on Undergraduate Low Student Patronage to Library Services

There is a close relationship between reading and university libraries. Books in the university library should be appealing and be current to ensure that students will read them. The libraries are places of opportunity where all students can strive to achieve success with the help of professional librarians who teach the use of library, study skills, information skills and strategies students need to become effective patrons of ideas and information. The academic achievement for all students, they need well equipped university libraries. Effective libraries services are a cost-efficient way to provide students with the skills and knowledge they will need to achieve in the twenty-first century. Humphrey (2008) stated that, in spite of all our techno innovations, there is no substitute for books when it comes to encouraging reading and expanding imagination, without access to books, academic success among students most definitely suffers. University libraries are keys to improving reading, the better the university libraries, the better students, therefore attention to university libraries must be an integral element in any plan for improvement of examination results.

Research Method

The study adopts descriptive survey design, the study was carried out in Sokoto State University, Sokoto. The population of the study comprises 2200 UG II Undergraduates, proportionate sampling technique was used to sample 321 with the view of getting adequate information regarding the "Effect of Social media on Undergraduates patronage to university library services. The questionnaire is a close ended one structured based on four-point rating scale. Data collected through self-structured questionnaire with 44 items, the instrument was face validated by three experts, one from measurement and evaluation and two experts from department of library and information science, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. The data collected was analyzed using percentage score.

Data Analysis

Research Question 1: What are the extent of using social media by undergraduates?

KEYS: VHE (very high extent) HE (high extent) LE (low extent) VLE (very low extent)

s/n	Items statement	VHE	HE	LE	VLE
1	Facebook	211(65.7%)	98(30.5%)	10(3.1%)	2(0.6%)
2	WhatsApp	198(61.6%)	100(31.1%)	16(4.9%)	7(2.1%)
3	Twitter	137(42.6%)	118(35.9%)	58(13.5%)	8(5.6%)
4	Badoo	123(38.3%)	95(29.5%)	61(19.0%)	42(13.0%)
5	Skype	111(34.5%)	97(30.2%)	68(21.1%)	45(14.0%)
6	Instagram	120(37.3%)	115(35.8%)	49(15.2%)	37(11.5%)
7	2 go	100(31.1%)	98(30.5%)	78(24.2%)	45(14.0%)
8	Palm chat	68(21.1%)	97(30.2%)	119(37.0%)	37(11.5%)
9	Messenger	158(49.2%)	141(43.9%)	16(4.9%)	6(1.8%)
10	You Tube	149(46.4%)	123(38.3%)	29(9.0%)	20(6.2%)
11	Ning	31(9.6%)	19(5.9%)	128(39.8%)	143(44.5%)
12	LinkedIn	173(53.8%)	121(37.6%)	19(5.9%)	8(5.6%)
13	Blog	161(50.1%)	111(34.5%)	32(9.9%)	17(5.2%)
14	Flickr	46(14.3%)	57(17.7%)	111(50.1%)	107(33.3%)
15	Second life	49(7.6%)	54(16.8%)	112(34.89)	106(33.0%)
16	Teacher tube	21(6.5%)	23(7.1%)	121(37.6%)	156(48.5%)
17	Net vibe	13(4.0%)	19(5.9%)	142(44.2%)	147(45.7%)
18	Deli.cio.us	175(5.2%)	216(6.5%)	133(41.4%)	150(46.7%)
19	Anobii	15(4.6%)	18(5.6%)	129(40.1%)	159(49.5%)
20	Connotea	17(5.2%)	18(5.6%)	126(39.2%)	160(49.8%)
21	Library thing	21(6.5%)	26(8.8%)	119(37.0%)	155(48.2%)
22	Lib.rari.us	10(3.1%)	16(4.9%)	146(45.4%)	149(46.4%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2021

The data gathered from table 1 above indicated that, 65.7% of the respondent are using Facebook at very high extent, 61.6% of the Undergraduates are using WhatsApp at very high extent, 42.6% of the respondents are using twitter at very high extent, 38.3% Undergraduates are using Badoo chat at very high extent, skype 34.5%, Instagram 37.3%, 2 go 31.1%, 21.1%, messenger 49.2%, and YouTube 46.4% are used by the Undergraduates at very high extent. Other social media sites that are used by the undergraduates at low extent includes Ning, Flickr, Net vibe, Second life, and Anobii respectively.

Research Question 2: What are the influence of Social media on undergraduates low patronage to library services?

Influence of Social Media on Undergraduates Low Patronage to University Library Services in Sokoto State University, Sokoto

KEYS: SA (strongly agree) A (agree) D (disagree) SD (strongly disagree)					
s/n	Items state	SA	A	D	SD
1	Social media distract student from their studies	195(60.7%)	97(30.2%)	21(6.5%)	8(2.4%)
2	Social media require spending of money like buying of data	192(59.8%)	70(21.8%)	32(9.9%)	27(8.4%)
3	Addiction to social media affect students' academic life	185(57.6%)	100(31.1%)	22(6.8%)	14(4.3%)
4	Social media activities do not allow student to patronize library services	200(62.3%)	72(22.4%)	30(9.3%)	19(5.9%)
5	Online games on social media denies students to concentrates on their studies	195(60.7%)	115(35.8%)	11(3.4%)	0(0.0%)
6	Social media affect students spelling	202(62.9%)	111(34.5%)	8(2.4%)	0(0.0%)
7	Extensive use of social media leads students to live in introversion	139(43.3%)	81(25.4%)	59(18.3%)	42(13.0%)
8	Time spent on social media can never be compared that of reading	190(59.1%)	100(31.1%)	25(7.7%)	6(1.8%)
9	Chatting denies students to benefit from the abundance resources in the library	183(57.0%)	136(42.3%)	2(0.6%)	0(0.0%)
10	Wasting of time is one of the attributes of social media	187(58.2%)	90(28.0%)	41(12.7%)	3(0.9%)
11	Extensive use of social media leads students to live in isolation	169(52.6%)	124(38.6%)	24(7.4%)	4(1.2%)
12	Social media activities contribute to the literacy	134(41.7%)	124(38.6%)	37(11.5%)	26(8.0%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2021

The data gathered from table 2 above indicated that, 62.9% of Undergraduates strongly agree that Social media activities do not allow student to patronize library services, 62.9% of the respondents strongly agree with Social media affect students spelling, 60.7% of the respondent strongly agree that Social media distract student from their studies, 59.8% strongly agree with Social media require spending of money like buying of data, 59.6% strongly agree with Addiction to social media affect students' academic life, 59.1% of the respondent also strongly agree Time spent on social media can never be compared that of reading books.

Research Question 3: What are the strategies to minimize the influence of social media on undergraduate low patronage to library services.

KEYS:					
	SA (strongly agree)	A (agree)	D (disagree)	SD (strongly disagree)	
S/N	Items statement	SA	A	D	SD
1	Librarians should adapt social media sites to disseminate information resources and services	206(64.1%)	94(29.2%)	19(5.9%)	2(0.6%)
2	Maximum time should not be given to social media compared to reading	196(61.0%)	70(31.7%)	51(9.6%)	4(3.7%)
3	Organize students group discussion reduces the effects	176(54.8%)	102(31.7%)	31(9.6%)	12(3.7%)
4	Librarians should adapt social media sites to market their services	192(59.8%)	68(21.1%)	54(16.8%)	7(2.1%)
5	Choosing end of semester as a dedicated time to use social media	145(45.1%)	111(34.5%)	42(13.0%)	23(7.1%)
6	Hybridization of library services is a strategy to improve students' patronage to library services	139(43.3%)	144(44.8%)	24(7.4%)	14(4.3%)
7	Librarians should educate students how to access library resources through social media	141(43.9%)	128(39.8%)	36(11.2%)	16(4.9%)
8	Teachers use social media to send assignment to students	196(61.0%)	91(28.4%)	22(6.8%)	12(3.7%)
9	Concentration on hard document minimize the effects of social media	150(46.7%)	100(31.1%)	51(15.8%)	20(6.2%)
10	Use social media site as means of sharing knowledge, rather than chatting, sending fun pictures and videos alone	141(43.9%)	112(34.8%)	39(12.1%)	29(9.0%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2021

The table 3 above reveals that 64.1% of the respondents strongly agree that Librarians should adapt social media sites to disseminate information resources and services, 61.0% of the respondent strongly agree that Maximum time should not be given to social media compared to reading books, 61.0% of the Undergraduates strongly agree Teachers use social media to send assignment to students 59.8% responses revealed that Librarians should adapt social media sites to market their services, 54.8% of the respondent agree with Organize students group discussion reduces the effects.

Discussion of findings

The data collected from the respondents indicated the extent of use of social media which includes: Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Badoo, Instagram, Messenger, YouTube are used by the Undergraduates at very high extent, that implies Undergraduates dedicated their time on social media which may eventually denied them to patronize University library services.

This was supported by Jaipuria, Jha, and Sinha (2016) are of the opinion that undergraduates are more probably affected by social media, which is very attractive as it gives university students another world to make friends, this inadvertently made students to love using social media. Social media are highly used by undergraduate students, wherever one sees undergraduate especially universities that provide free Wi-Fi and or those afford to buy data to their phone or laptop, they may be serious chatting or browsing on WhatsApp, Facebook, Messenger, Instagram, Twitter and so on. Similarly, Ekere, Omekwu and Odoh (2014) Pointed out some dangers associated with the social media sites such as e-crime, internet addiction, laziness, fraud, murder, kidnapping, immoral act like phonography, prostitution cyber-bullying among others.

The findings of the study revealed the effect of social media on Undergraduates which includes: Social media activities do not allow Undergraduates to patronize University library services, Social media affect students spelling, Social media distract student from their studies, Social media require spending of money like buying of data, Addiction to social media affect students' academic life, Time spent on social media can never be compared that of reading books. This is line with idea of Neal (2012) Who describes social media as easy-to use services which hinder student to patronize library services, because student use it to interact with other people online such as Facebook, YouTube, Blog, Twitter and so on and so forth. Therefore, using social media is easy and simple services, it consumes time and enable one to create online presence very easily as signing up for Facebook and Twitter account. Similarly, Jha, Jaipuria, Jha and Sinha (2016) asserted that students are more probably affected by social media to some extent, it absolutely affects the lives of undergraduate university student's academic performance.

The finding also made it clear that Librarians should adapt social media sites to disseminate information resources and services, Maximum time should not be given to social media compared to reading books, Teachers use social media to send assignment to students, Librarians should adapt social media sites to market their services and Organize students group discussion reduces the effects. This was supported by Kolan and Dzandza (2018) argued some strategies that could apply to minimize the influence of social media among student. There should be some strict policy regarding to the access of such sites; the students should encourage to follow the positive aspects of social media in order to obtain positive information, seminars should be organized in the various schools or faculties to enlighten students more about the possible implications of social media usage on their academic performance; students should make sure that they use these social networking sites judiciously to ensure that they do not become detrimental to their academics; librarians/lecturers can adopt new strategies by channeling assignments or discussions on social media platforms to help inculcate the habit of reading and using these sites for academic work; students must minimize the time they spend on social media, patronize library services to avoid being obsessed by these sites for unnecessary chatting;

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Librarians should adapt social media sites to disseminate information resources and services.
2. Librarians should promote reading habit among undergraduates by organizing literacy activities such as book discussion, library orientation, these would minimize the influence of social media among Undergraduates.
3. Undergraduates should pursue an excellent academic performance, frequent library patronage and gain adequate knowledge that will help them in the future.
4. Conclusion
5. This study investigated influence of social media on undergraduate low patronage of library services in Sokoto State University, Sokoto. The findings disclose that Social media and other technological devices has influence on undergraduates' attitude towards the regular and effective use of university library services.

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